

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

PLAN OVERVIEW

A Data Management Plan created using DMPonline

Title: Promoting soil fertility, yield and income in smallholder agriculture of semiarid and arid Mediterranean regions by management of beneficial soil microbiota, conservation agriculture and intercropping

Acronym: ProSmallAgriMed

Creator: Guido Lingua

Principal Investigator: Guido Lingua

Data Manager: Guido Lingua

Affiliation: Università degli Studi del Piemonte Orientale "Amedeo Avogadro"

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ORCID ID: 0000-0003-3157-4376

Project abstract:

The project ProSmallAgriMed aims to promote the rational use of beneficial soil microbiota and improve small farmer agronomic practices to enhance productivity of inter-cropped perennial (cactus pear) and short-term species (field crops and vegetables) and promote synergistic cooperation between farmers and the value chain. The optimization of such practices in water limited environments will contribute to food security by (1) enhancing carbon sequestration and ensuring soil fertility; (2) expanding land coverage in space and time, thus supporting soil conservation and water use efficiency; (3) improving yields for consumption as food, feed, or industrial transformation; (4) increasing the nutritional quality of crop products; and (5) guaranteeing water and soil quality by decreasing chemical inputs. Such goals will be pursued by stimulating smallholder associations by increasing their expert knowledge and ability to interact each other and with various actors of the value chain, and by modulating new agronomic practices to be tested in real-life field conditions. The technological transfer to Maghreb farmers of know-how in the improvement of water efficiency and use of targeted beneficial soil microbial inocula will give farmers a competitive advantage in production of high-quality products and promote the establishment of start-ups specialised in the production of targeted inocula, based on indigenous beneficial soil microbes. Results will provide a model that can be extended to the sustainable production of other crops in water-limited agro-ecosystems and will be instrumental in upgrading (i) the social and economic conditions of farmers and of the countries hosting new enterprises; (ii) the ecological conditions of semiarid and arid areas, through reduction of chemical inputs, soil erosion and water loss and increased resilience to climate change; and (iii) the ability of smallholder farmers to drain important agronomic information from similar areas.

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PROMOTING SOIL FERTILITY, YIELD AND INCOME IN SMALLHOLDER AGRICULTURE OF SEMIARID AND ARID MEDITERRANEAN REGIONS BY MANAGEMENT OF BENEFICIAL SOIL MICROBIOTA, CONSERVATION AGRICULTURE AND INTERCROPPING – PROSMALLAGRIMED

1. DATA SUMMARY

1. Purpose of the data collection / generation

Data will originate from experimentation and will be used to assess the effectiveness of the proposed technology, i.e. the intercropping of cactus pear plant with annual plants in the presence of beneficial soil microbes, in increasing the yield for small farm holders. Data will also be collected to assess the quality of products, to describe the farmers availability to introduce the proposed technology (by means of interviews) and to describe the social and economic conditions in the interested areas. Finally, models describing the possible environmental and economic advantages will be produced.

2. Relation to the objectives of the project

Experimental data will be essential to reach the objectives of the project.

3. Types and formats of the data generated collected

Data will be in the format of spreadsheet, tables, reports, pictures, links, models, handbooks. Formats may include files of the following types: portable document format, excel files, jpg or tiff pictures, web sites.

4. Specify if existing data will be reused

Most data will be original and originating from the project. They will consist of experimental data from lab and field experiments, and interviews. Existing data will be used for bibliographic research and the preparation of reviews and systematic maps.

6. Data utility

Data originating from the project will be useful to researchers, farmers, associations of producers, policy makers, stakeholders.

2. FAIR DATA

For publications and any other dissemination and communication activities the following metadata will be included:

- 1) the term "PRIMA";
- 2) the acronym of the project and the project grant number;
- 3) the publication date, and the length of the embargo period, if applicable;
- 4) the persistent identifier (e.g. DOI – Digital Object identifier), when applicable.

All pertinent documents related to the project ProSmallAgriMed will be made available to all partners in the project, mainly using the Google Drive project folder (accessible to the partners only)

All the datasets will be confidential until publication. A consensual decision will be taken by the ProSmallAgriMed consortium on which datasets should be published, after having carefully examined IPR protection of the generated knowledge and exploitation issues.

For appropriate preservation and sharing of internal data and datasets, ProSmallAgriMed will use a Google Drive project folder (for consortium Members only, meaning Beneficiaries and Partner Organisations).

Beneficiaries/Partner Organisations will provide selective access to their drives (e.g. Google Drive and Microsoft OneDrive) only within the consortium, according to their internal procedures. Raw data from analytical instruments will need the providers' software, which must be licensed and cannot be made openly accessible, so they will be converted to any acceptable generic format if possible. All remaining data shall be converted into common file formats (docx, .xlsx, .pdf, .jpg, etc.). This implies that no additional specific software will be required.

After careful evaluation of the above-mentioned issues, data eligible for publication will be publicly available in an aggregated form on a digital platform, such as Zenodo or other highly cited public repositories complying with the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data principles and using Creative Commons licenses options. The platform and the data format will be chosen to make them as easily accessible as possible, using standard formats (for Windows, macOS and Linux) that do not require particular software, whenever possible. Otherwise, documentation on how to access the data on the chosen digital platform will be created and made publicly available.

During the collection phase, all data collected and maintained by partners will be subject to the internally established Guidelines for data management to ensure that all researchers will keep up the principles of lawful and ethical data management and end users can trust the system with their personal data.

We will adhere to common standards for formats, ensuring that they are compliant as much as possible with available (open) software applications and in particular, we will give attention to facilitating re-combinations with different datasets from different origins.

Metadata, data standards, names, and extensions of data sets will be agreed upon and shared among the consortium along with the progress of research activities. Standard naming conventions for datasets, reporting, sample mailings, and other documents shall be used as indicated above.

Data licensing will be considered when appropriate and if compliant with the regulatory framework. Primarily data is not licensed, and it is planned to be used internally for consortium only.

Data will be available for third parties according to the formats, timing and licenses specified in the Consortium Agreement.

The ProSmallAgriMed consortium will seek a consensual decision on the application of an embargo period and the length of such period, after having examined IPR protection and exploitation issues and with the goal of making the data available as soon as possible.

All PROSMALLAGRIMED partners are strongly committed to ensuring data quality, in keeping with the scientific rigor espoused by their organizations. This includes data validity, reliability, precision, integrity, and timeliness. Data curation will be the responsibility of the partner that generated it. Specifically for the survey data, standard data cleaning, and quality-checking processes will be carried out before data analysis, including internal review processes and double-checking/cross-referencing survey questions with the information provided elsewhere in the survey.

Datasets will be stored on the partner's private secure servers and shall be accessible to all consortium members with no expected limitations for data reuse in research. Data shall be available for a minimum period of 5 years from the end of the project.

IPR issues will be carefully considered during the project and 5 five years from termination, and then the re-usable data will be submitted to OpenAire-funded research data archive Zenodo.

The research outputs generated by ProSmallAgriMed will consist of academic papers, policy briefs, databases, reports, and summarising and disseminating the main research results. All research output available on the ProSmallAgriMed website is free of charge. The ProSmallAgriMed consortium will allocate significant attention to coordinating the intellectual property rights (IPR) related to exploitation and dissemination. The consortium has adopted the position of open by default. Nonetheless, exceptions may occur were for commercial, security, data-protection, or legal issues, certain information or results must remain confidential. The project will work under the guiding principle whereby the results generator has full ownership of them. Joint ownership will be clarified to the maximum extent possible through a clear and agreed work breakdown. Where individual ownership is indiscernible, all joint owners have the right to royalty-free exploitation of the results. The scientific publications produced within PROSMALLAGRIMED will be available as open access and freely available via either 'gold' or 'green' open access models, where the standard approach will be to follow the 'green' route to open access. This means that copies of publications will be deposited before, alongside, or after their publication. The "gold" route will be followed when the partners identify a strategic rationale for doing so (e.g., significantly greater impact will be achieved through open-access publication by the publisher). Criteria of cost and value will be used on a case-by-case basis.

3. ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

The Grant Agreement allocates costs for research time dedicated to data collection and analysis to the partners as well as golden open access costs. We do not envisage additional costs for making data FAIR and ensuring long-term access for third parties. All scientific publications will be available either via the “gold” or “green” open-access models.

The partners generally follow a decentralised approach to data management, meaning that aspects such as individual partners’ trusted repositories will be supervised by the individual partners. Each partner will therefore also have responsibility for the work with their own data, following the applicable national and EU regulations, while quality control of the data used also falls under the responsibility of the partners leading the respective WP.

For the trusted repositories used by individual partners, the responsibility for these repositories is decentralised, i.e. ascribed to the individual partner making use of the given responsibility. UPO will supervise this and hold overarching responsibility for the data management within the project, with the exceptions described below. UPO will not be responsible for:

- disruptions, losses or any damage to data stored on Google Drive or any of the other trusted repositories used by individual partners that are due to force majeure;
- any misuse of data created or collected by a partner;
- quality of data included in the trusted repositories;
- any breach of internal obligations or international/national legislation committed by a partner;
- data or documents not duly reviewed internally;
- any excessive costs incurred by a partner when publishing via gold Open Access.

As regards long term preservation, PROSMALLAGRIMED project website will continue to be online at least up until three years after project closure to secure continuity and the sustainability of long-term impact. All documents/data stored in Google Drive and the other trusted repositories used by individual partners will have a permanent link.

4. DATA SECURITY

The following provisions will be implemented for data security.

Access control:

- Unauthorised Persons have no access to data and data processing systems.
- Authentication and authorization with individual access rights provided only to project partners.

5. ETHICAL ASPECTS

Ethical or legal implications related to data sharing are addressed within the ethical and legal framework of ProSmallAgriMed, based on the EU GDPR, Horizon Europe ethical standards and guidelines, and the national legal frameworks in force. It is essential to note that WP leaders are responsible for their WP activities. Whenever there are doubts about ethical implications, WP leaders must consult the project coordinator UPO. Interviews and surveys will be done in line with ethical principles, including explicitly asking in each interview or online survey if the information provided can be used for research purposes and if we can use it for creating publicly available data tables with a certain level of aggregation. We strictly enforce the protection of necessary nonymisation and any confidential information we might get during the interviews. Building trust is a key element of the survey process and facilitates a more significant response rate in the second round. Overall, in the case of handling sensitive data, ProSmallAgriMed will follow EU and national laws regarding ethical principles and data protection, in particular, the European General Data Protection Regulation – (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR). Quantitative data will be collected and handled at the participants’ institutions under pre-agreed rules and protocols, according to the best practices of the field.